

The Influence of E-service Quality and Social Presence on Repurchase Intention through Customer Trust

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Abstract

This research analyzes the influence of e-service quality, social presence, customer trust, and repurchase intention in the TokopediaPlay Live stream Shopping application. This research is guided by grand theory, namely the Theory of Planned Behavior or TPB and Consumer Behavior. This research uses a quantitative approach with the type of explanatory research. The sample used was Tokopedia Play student users in Surabaya, totaling 190 respondents. Data were collected using a questionnaire with a Likert scale consisting of five points. The analysis method in this research uses Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) based on Partial Least Square (PLS) with the help of SmartPLS 3 software. The results show that e-service quality does not affect repurchase intention. Social presence influences repurchase intention. E-service quality and social presence affect customer trust. Customer trust is a perfect mediation variable (complete mediation) between the e-service quality variable and repurchase intention. Customer trust is a partial mediation variable between the social presence variable and repurchase intention.

1. Introduction

The marketplace, part of e-commerce, is where commercial interactions occur between sellers who directly offer goods and services to consumers. Marketplaces provide many advantages, including that sellers do not need to create their own website or online shop. Several of the best marketplaces in Indonesia are market leaders, including Shopee, Tokopedia, Bukalapak, Lazada, JD: ID, and Blibli. The significant growth of marketplace sites in Indonesia certainly causes competition with each other. Shopee and Tokopedia are Indonesia's two biggest e-commerce brands that have

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succeeded in becoming top of mind for consumers. Tokopedia has been the most visited e-commerce for five years (2018-2022), although in 2020, its position was shifted by Shopee (Iprice.co.id).

The significant growth of marketplace sites in Indonesia certainly causes competition with each other. One of the methods marketplaces use to increase interaction between consumers and sellers and conversions continues to emerge, one of which is live-streaming shopping. Live streaming shopping allows streamers to display products in real-time video, interact with viewers in real-time, improve communication friendliness to provide more detailed product information to customers, enable customers to observe the appearance and personality of the seller, and on the consumer side to judge the extent of the seller can identify with them and empathize with their needs, which will help the audience better understand the product they want. To increase the interactive atmosphere, Live Streamer shows several appearances, functions, and introductions of related products directly. Consumers can ask product prices, shipping, and other questions because consumers can not only view text messages and images but also watch real-time videos and interact with sellers in real-time (Ming et al., 2021; Sun et al., 2019; Wongkitrungrueng & Assarut, 2018).

When users watch a shopping live stream, they can receive various information on their smartphone screens, including visual and audio effects delivered by the streamer, real-time viewer count, text messages from other viewers, and gifts donated by other viewers. In other words, users feel the presence of others when watching live streaming, and the concept of social presence should apply to this situation (Luc & Shin, 2021). *Live stream shopping* is a new marketing strategy that has increased in recent years; not only can display products in real-time to the audience, but also sellers can respond to potential buyers more quickly and can convert these potential buyers to buy or rebuy (Wang et al., 2021) In live stream shopping sales, the user's visual experience becomes more real. It can efficiently fulfill the user's shopping entertainment goals to improve their shopping experience (Liu et al., 2020).

Tokopedia live stream shopping, called Tokopedia Play, was released in May 2019. Tokopedia provides several features in live shopping. First, streamers can direct promotions with videos to viewers and show actual products being sold. Second, a chat feature allows potential consumers to interact directly with the chat. The three shop vouchers are displayed directly to attract potential buyers. Fourth is product tagging, displaying superior products so potential buyers can see them. The fifth feature is free shipping, which allows users to get goods or buy an item without paying shipping costs. The six COD or Cash On Delivery features allow buyers to pay for products when the goods arrive at home. The seventh voucher and cashback, voucher, and cashback to cut your next payment or shopping (Tokopedia.com).

However, in reality, despite the many features provided and even though Tokopedia is the top 2 most frequently visited marketplace according to Iprice data in the first quarter of 2022, in the Live stream shopping feature, its position is still in fourth position after Tiktok and Instagram. According to the results of the 2022 Opinion Poll (JakPat) survey, it shows that 83.7% of Indonesian people have watched online shopping features based on live stream shopping with the numbers Shopee (83.4%), TikTok (42.2%), Instagram (34.1 %), Tokopedia (30.4%) and Facebook (25.9%) (Databoks, 2022). In 2023, Tokopedia users will decrease consecutively for three months. In February 2023, Tokopedia recorded a total of 108.1 million visits. This figure decreased by 15.60% monthly from 128.1 million visits in January 2023 (Databoks, 2023). This decrease in visits could impact purchase intentions to return to the Tokopedia application; because of this decrease, it is assumed that some consumers will not visit the Tokopedia application in the following month.

Repurchase intention is an essential variable for a company. According to Hawkins et al. (2019), the company's current goal is to increase sales and retain customers by paying attention to consumer behavior after purchasing the product or service and making customers make repeat purchases. According to Peter & Olson, (2010), Customers who are satisfied and believe in the service provided

by the company will repurchase the product, praise the product they bought in front of other people, be less interested in competitors' brands and advertisements, and buy other products from the same company. According to Buttle, (2009), If customers are satisfied, trust will grow while risk and uncertainty are reduced. Therefore, trust is the glue that holds relationships together across time and experience. Repurchase intentions for live stream shopping can be increased by improving e-service quality and social presence that add value and are of high quality.

A service-focused strategy is one of the success factors for surviving in today's competitive electronic environment (Blut, 2016; Rita et al., 2019). According to (Zeithaml et al., 2017a), *e-service quality* is defined as the ability of an online shopping platform to assist in the form of a shopping experience, payment in a transaction or purchase of goods, and product delivery effectively and efficiently. E-service quality dimensions are website design, customer service, fulfillment, and privacy (Rita et al., 2019). Companies must provide superior service experiences to their customers so that they will repurchase and be loyal to the company (Gounaris et al., 2010). According to (Peter & Olson, 2010), The quality and value of a product or service are essential in increasing repurchase intentions, which involve functional, experiential, and psychosocial benefits. In line with research (Areiza & Galindo, 2022; Khatib et al., 2019; Shin et al., 2013), the quality of electronic services that customers perceive nicely will form a good value perception about a company. Consumer perceptions of e-service quality are part of the overall assessment of all services provided by the company.

The unique characteristic of live streaming is that consumers can interact with sellers in real-time, resulting in a shopping experience where consumers feel like they are in a virtual world and can interact directly with that world as if there is no separation between the virtual world and the natural world (immersive). and engaging and more interpersonal connections (Wohn & Freeman, 2020). Given the real-time immersion of live streaming, consumers can feel the social presence and social/human touch even without actual human contact (Gefen & Straub, 2004). Because consumers interact with computer-mediated media and communicate with other people involved in those communities, the more transparent the shopping environment, the greater the security customers feel when making purchasing decisions (Lee & Park, 2014). Several studies have confirmed that social presence has a positive effect on usage decisions and reuse intentions in online platforms (Alhulail et al., 2019; Attar et al., 2023; Fang et al., 2018; Lim et al., 2021; Ma, 2021).

This research will focus on e-service quality, social presence, and customer trust, essential factors influencing repurchase interest in live-stream shopping-based sales. Tokopedia has been the most visited e-commerce site for five years (2018-2022). However, in live stream shopping-based sales, it is still in fourth position as a live shopping platform in Indonesia. In 2023, Tokopedia will also experience a decrease in the number of visitors (Databoks, 2023). The decrease in visitors impacts transactions carried out by consumers; consumer transactions are part of the purchasing decision process, including the intention to repurchase. Reuse intentions can be increased by improving value-added and high-quality e-service quality (Areiza & Galindo, 2022; Khatib et al., 2019; Shin et al., 2013). In previous research, we ignored social presence. In contrast, in this research, we added the social presence variable because livestream shopping is part of s-commerce, which consists of three main characteristics: technology based on social media, social interaction, and business/commercial activities (Huang & Benyoucef, 2013) addition of the mediating variable of consumer trust because trust is a multidimensional construct of beliefs and intentions towards beliefs (Lee & Park, 2014).

This research is supported by the grand theory of TPB (Ajzen & Fishbein, 2004) and Consumer Behavior (Kotler & Armstrong, 2017). This research will be conducted in Surabaya because Surabaya is one of Indonesia's three cities with the most Tokopedia users. (Tokopedia.com) From the similar web survey data, the most significant % of Tokopedia users, amounting to 39.63%, are aged 18-24 years. For this reason, the sample used was undergraduate students using Tokopedia Play in

Surabaya. After explaining the problem phenomena and theories that will be used and the research gaps from previous research, this research has its originality.

2. Theoretical Review

The Theory of Planned Behavior

The Theory of Planned Behavior shows that intention is a direct antecedent of behavior (Ajzen, 2020). Intentions are determined by attitudes towards the behavior, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control, which impact behavioral beliefs, normative beliefs, and control beliefs. Behavioral beliefs, normative beliefs, and control beliefs can vary as a function of various background factors, namely individual (personality, mood emotion, intelligence, values, general attitudes, experience), social (education, age, gender income, culture), and information (knowledge), media, and Intervention). According to (Ajzen & Fishbein, 2004). Attitude towards behavior refers to the level of an individual's positive or negative evaluation or assessment of the perceived experience of a given company's performance. Subjective norm is how consumers are influenced by their environment, reference groups, family, and sales force; perceived behavioral control is an expected outcome of engaging in a particular behavior, and evaluation of outcomes involves assessing the likelihood of consequences, such as the ease or difficulty consumers feel in getting product information from vendor websites and purchasing products from web vendors. Positive attitudes and supportive subjective norms motivate one to engage in certain intentional behaviors. However, this can only be achieved if perceived control over behavior is strong enough. Understanding consumers' repurchase intentions is very important because their final purchasing behavior can be predicted from their intentions (Ajzen, 2020).

Repurchase intention

According to (Peter & Olson, 2010), repurchase intention is purchasing activities carried out more than once or several times. A positive purchasing experience increases the likelihood of repurchase at the same store. For this reason, the quality and value of a product or service are essential in increasing repurchase intentions. They involve functional, experiential, and psychosocial benefits. According to (Hawkins et al., 2019), the company's current goal is not only to increase sales but also to retain customers and make customers make repeat purchases. After initial use, cognitive beliefs, such as an individual's perception of a system's usefulness and satisfaction, may change, leading to repeat behavior or discontinued use. Among these two constructs, Repurchase Intention is a customer's goal to maintain a relationship with a service provider and purchase a product or service. Next time from the same provider (Kitapci et al., 2014).

Customer Trust

Customer Trust is defined as the general belief that another party in a social exchange will behave in an ethical and socially appropriate manner, and will not act opportunistically (Gefen et al., 2003; S. C. Kim, 2019). According to (Buttle, 2009) Developing trust is an investment in building relationships that have long-term results. In online-based sales, consumer trust is divided into two, namely individual trust (trust in the seller) and institutional trust (trust in the platform/marketplace), because consumer purchasing decisions will be made if consumers trust the seller and the platform (Lu et al., 2016). Trust has been widely recognized as an important determinant of purchasing behavior, as it helps reduce perceived risk and thereby increases

consumers' willingness to engage with a seller through the provider's reputation, perceived level of personalization, or information provided (Lauterbach et al., 2009; Zibarzani et al., 2022); According to (CKnight et al., 2002) e-trust depends on security assurance, reputation, web search, fulfillment (e.g. willingness to customize), presentation (for example web quality), technology, and interaction (for example e-forums). According to (Buttle, 2009), there are three key attributes in building trust, namely benevolence, competence and integrity.

E-Service Quality

According to (Zeithaml et al., 2002) e-service quality not only includes the experience during consumer interaction with a website but also post-interaction service aspects. One of the most obvious differences between traditional service quality and e-service quality is the replacement of interpersonal interactions with human-machine interactions. The theory from (Zeithaml et al., 2017b) e-service quality measures how much the online shopping platform is able to provide assistance in the form of a shopping experience, payment in a transaction or purchase of goods, and product delivery effectively and efficiently. (Hawkins et al., 2019; Wolfinbarger & Gilly, 2003) e-service quality indicators include fulfillment, website design, privacy/security and customer service. According to (Hawkins et al., 2019) web design includes factors such as information quality, navigation, price, merchandise availability, purchasing process, and message tracking. In (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, et al., 2005) fulfillment includes the accuracy of the service promises provided, product stock availability, and delivery of ordered products according to the time promised by the platform. Customer service refers to a site's ability to maintain relationships with customers when problems arise in transactions (Santos, 2003). In (Zeithaml et al., 2017) privacy includes the level of site security and protecting customer information from being given to any other party.

Social Presence

Presence is a subjective sensation felt by media users. Presence is important during virtual reality experiences. Presence occurs when using all types of media. Presence is divided into two, namely telepresence and social presence. Social presence is a form of consumer ability to be identified in a group, communicate openly, and be able to establish relationships involving feelings (emotions) as in relationships outside the virtual world (Bickle et al., 2019). Technically, Social presence is defined by the platform's capacity to convey nonverbal cues (personal, social elements) and human warmth. Because buyers often need social cues from sellers and other buyers to support their purchasing decisions, a lack of social presence can hinder online exchanges (Khwaja et al., 2019). because consumers not only interact with computer-mediated media, but also need to communicate with other consumers and engage in these communities. Specifically, social presence reflects the extent to which people build warm and personal connections with each other through media (Lee & Park, 2014).

From the buyer's perspective in live stream shopping sales, social presence is manifested in three dimensions: Social presence live stream shopping platform, the extent to which consumers feel a sense of warmth and trust in salespeople, vendors, products, channels and companies (Gefen & Straub, 2004; Ye et al., 2020). Social presence viewers, represents the extent to which consumers are aware of the presence or whereabouts of other consumers. In live streaming trading, viewers can find out about products or through e-WOM other viewers. Communication between consumers during live streaming makes online shopping more social, thereby reducing the feeling of unreality (Kian, 2014; Pavlou et al., 2007; Ye et al., 2020). Streamers' social presence platform, the extent to which customers

perceive the personal characteristics and sensitivity of service providers through online platforms, closes the psychological distance between viewers and streamers, and can help viewers better understand the products they want, thereby increasing viewers' sense of trust and engagement (Lu et al., 2016; Ming et al., 2021).

Research Hypothesis

- H1: e-service quality has a positive influence on repurchase intention
- H2: social presence has a positive influence on repurchase intention
- H3: e-service quality has a positive influence on customer trust
- H4: social presence has a positive influence on customer trust
- H5: customer trust has a positive influence on repurchase intention
- H6: E-service quality influences repurchase intention through customer trust
- H7: social presence influences repurchase intention through customer trust

The conceptual framework for this research was prepared by connecting the results of previous research with theoretical studies so that the problems in this research can be formulated in a problem statement which is then realized into a research conceptual model which is shown to answer the research hypothesis, as seen in the following picture:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of Research

3. Materials and Methods

This research uses a quantitative approach with explanatory research because it wants to get an explanation of the relationship or cause and effect between existing variables through hypothesis testing (Sekaran & Bougie, 2017). The sampling technique used in this research is Probability Sampling using purposive sampling. Respondents in this study are undergraduate students who live in Surabaya aged 18-25 years and consumers who have visited the Tokopedia Play application and have made a transaction at least once in the last six months. The number of samples used is significant. One hundred ninety respondents will be used. Data collection uses a questionnaire with a Likert scale consisting of five points. The questionnaire was distributed from April 2023 to September 2023 via Google Form and was distributed offline. The analysis method in this research uses Structural Equation Modeling (SEM based on Partial Least Square (PLS) with the help of SmartPLS 3 software. All indicators used to measure the variables in this research were adopted from several previous

studies. Service Quality variable with four indicators, namely web design with 7 question items adopted from (Holloway & Beatty, 2003; Loiacono et al., 2007; Rita et al., 2019), fulfillment with 4 question items adopted from (Blut, 2016 Holloway & Beatty, 2003), customer service with 3 question items adopted from (Parasuraman, Zeitham, et al., 2005; Rita et al., 2019) and privacy indicators with 3 question items adopted from (Blut, 2016; Rita et al., 2019).

The social presence variable was also adopted from several previous studies with three indicators, namely social presence platform with 3 question items, social presence of other viewers, and social presence of streamers adopted from research (Gefen et al., 2003; Lu et al., 2016; Ming et al., 2021; Ye et al., 2020). The following variable is customer trust with three indicators: Benevolence with 2 question items, Integrity with 2 question items, and Competence with 3 question items adopted from research(Lu et al., 2016; Ming et al., 2021). The final research variable is repurchase intention with three indicators, namely Purchase Frequency with 2 question items, Consumer Commitment with 2 question items, and Positive Recommendation with 1 question item adopted from research (Rita et al., 2019).

4. Results and Discussions

Statistical data analysis in this research uses the SEM method based on Partial Least Square (PLS) with two stages, namely outer model analysis or measurement model analysis followed by inner model evaluation or structural model evaluation (Hair et al., 2017). To test whether the indicator is valid or not in measuring variables, use convergent validity by looking at the outer loading or loading factor value. If it is $>0.6-0.7$, it can be declared valid (Chin, 1998) and using discriminant validity, it is calculated by looking at the cross loading value in an indicator. corresponds to greater than the correlation value of the indicator with other variables. A variable is said to be valid if $AVE > 0.50$. Meanwhile, to test the reliability of variables, it is measured using two criteria, namely composite reliability and Cronbach alpha. A variable is declared reliable if the composite reliability value is above 0.70 or the Cronbach alpha value is above 0.60 (Hair et al., 2017).

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Structural model analysis was carried out to convince researchers that the model built was accurate (Hair et al., 2017). The structural model in PLS was evaluated using the following indicators Determination Coefficient (R²), Predictive Relevance (Q²) and Goodness of Fit Index (GoF). The results from table 3 show the results of the structural model analysis. Where is the Coefficient of Determination (R²) to assess the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The higher the R² value, the better the predictive model and research model carried out. The Q² value is used to measure how good the observations produced by the research model are. Measured from:

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - R1^2) \times (1 - R2^2)$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - 0,794) \times (1 - 0,727) = 0,943$$

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE	R ²	Q ²
X1 (e-service quality)	0,949	0,954	0,550		
X2 (social presence)	0,900	0,918	0,556		
Z (customer trust)	0,883	0,909	0,588	0,794	0,943
Y (repurchase intention)	0,880	0,912	0,676	0,727	

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

The Q² value is 0.943, which shows that the contribution of the diversity of research variables is 94.3%, while the remaining 5.7% is explained by other variables outside this research. The GoF coefficient must have a value range of 0 to 1. The closer it is to 1, the higher the level of accuracy of the model. The goodness of fit value based on table 2 and table 3 above can be calculated as follows.

$$GoF = \sqrt{AVE \times R^2}$$

$$GoF = 0,670 = 67\%$$

The GoF calculation result is 0.670 or 67%. These results indicate that the model obtained is good at making predictions. This means that the model has a high ability to explain empirical data (>0.36) (Hair et al., 2017).

Hypothesis Test

Hypothesis testing is carried out using PLS analysis and by looking at the results of the t-statistical test or significance value. Hypothesis testing using statistical values in PLS is carried out using the Bootstrapping method; the hypothesis can be accepted if the tstatistic value > t-table (1.96) or p-value < 0.05 (5% significance level)

Table 2. Direct and Indirect Hypothesis Tests

	Path coefficient/ Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
E-service quality → Repurchase Intention	0,188	1,916	0,056	Not significant
Social Presence → Repurchase intention	0,272	3,189	0,002	significant
E-service quality → Customer trust	0,514	9,996	0,000	significant

Social Presence → Customer trust	0,444	8,418	0,000	significant
Customer trust → Repurchase intention	0,449	4,737	0,000	significant
E-service quality → customer trust → Repurchase Intention	0,231	4,286	0,000	significant (complete)
Social presence → customer trust → Repurchase Intention	0,199	4,228	0,000	significant (partial)

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

Table 2 shows that the direction of the relationship between e-service quality and repurchase intention is positive but insignificant. This means that the higher the e-service quality, the higher the repurchase intention, which is insignificant. This insignificant relationship can be seen from the t-statistics of e-service quality on repurchase intention of $1.916 < 1.96$ or from the p-value of $0.056 > 0.05$. However, it is positively related because the original sample value is 0.188, which indicates that the direction of the relationship between social presence and repurchase intention is positive. Therefore, H1 is rejected. Then, the t-statistics value of social presence on repurchase intention is $3.189 > 1.96$, or can be seen from the p-value of $0.001 < 0.05$. The original sample value was 0.272, which indicates that the direction of the relationship between social presence and repurchase intention is positive. Therefore, H2 is accepted so that the higher the social presence in the minds of consumers, the higher the repurchase intention made by consumers. Furthermore, the t-statistics value of e-service quality on customer trust is $9.996 > 1.96$, or can be seen from the p-value, $0.000 < 0.05$. The original sample value was 0.514. Shows that the direction of the relationship between e-service quality and customer trust is positive. Therefore, H3 is accepted, so the better the company's e-service quality, the more trust consumers have in the company.

Table 2 also shows that the t-statistics value of social presence on customer trust is $8.418 > 1.96$, or can be seen from the p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$. The original sample value was 0.444. Shows that the direction of the relationship between social presence and customer trust is positive. Therefore, H4 is accepted so that the higher the social presence in the minds of consumers, the more trust consumers have in the company. Furthermore, the t-statistics value of customer trust on repurchase intention is $4.737 > 1.96$, or can be seen from the p-value, $0.000 < 0.05$. The original sample value was 0.449. Shows that the direction of the relationship between customer trust and repurchase intention is positive. Therefore, H5 is accepted, so the higher the trust consumers have in the company, the higher the repurchase intention consumers make.

Table 2 also shows the indirect relationship between variables, which shows that there is an indirect influence between the e-service quality variable (X1) on repurchase intention (Y) through the customer trust variable (Z), which has a path coefficient of 0.231, with a t-statistic value of 4.286 (>1.96) and p-values 0.000 (<0.05). These results indicate that the indirect influence of the e-service quality variable on repurchase intention is through. The customer trust variable is positive and significant. Thus, H6 is accepted, namely customer trust mediates the influence of e-service quality on repurchase intention. Furthermore, there is an indirect influence between the social presence variable (X2) on repurchase intention (Y) through the customer trust variable (Z) which has a path coefficient of 0.199, with a t-statistic value of 4.228 (>1.96) and p-values of 0.000 (< 0.05). These results indicate that the indirect influence of the social presence variable on repurchase intention through the customer trust variable is positive and significant. Thus, H7 is accepted, namely customer trust mediates the influence of social presence on repurchase intention.

Discussion

The results of analysis and testing show that the quality of Tokopediaplay electronic services that consumers feel when purchasing on the Tokopediaplay application cannot increase their intention to repurchase in the future on the same application. This is because the respondents in this study are students, where in this era of information and technology they will consider several services from several live stream shopping platforms that they have used. For this reason, they will use and repurchase on live stream shopping platforms that have service quality that creates a perceived experience which according to them has a higher perception of added value than other platforms and has superior service quality attributes. According to the results of the e-service quality variable which has a low outer loading value, there are web design indicators which include information quality, website aesthetics, purchasing process, website comfort, product choice, price offer. Users will leave a website if it is difficult to use, illegible, does not answer user questions, or is generally less interesting (Haghighinasab & Tabeien, 2008). Customers rate their experience using a website to assess the overall service quality of an online store. According to (Peter & Olson, 2010). Positive purchasing experiences increase repeat purchases at the same store. If the most recent experience is negative, overall feelings about the company will diminish, and repurchase intentions will decrease significantly. For this reason, the quality and value of a product or service is very important in increasing repurchase intentions which involve functional, experiential and psychosocial benefits.

The research results are in line with research by (Meitiana & Sembhodo, 2022) which shows that E-Service Quality does not have a significant effect on repurchase intention because there is no difference between customer expectations for electronic service performance before using the service and brand perceptions of the service received. However, this is in contrast to research conducted by (Nopreza & Sumadi, 2022) which shows that e-service quality influences repurchase intention, when e-commerce provides the best service, customers will also think about making another purchase because they have had a good shopping experience. well before. With good quality e-service, customers will be able to shop more efficiently. Supported by research by (Shin et al., 2013) shows that even if customer satisfaction, customer trust, and customer commitment are good, poor website service quality can have a negative impact on customers' future repurchase intentions.

The results of this research show that the Tokopediaplay e-service quality consumers feel when using the Tokopediaplay application increases consumer trust in the same application because of the experience consumers feel. It cannot be separated from the four privacy indicators that consumers feel safe shopping at TokopediaPlay because they can implement a security system on the site to protect consumers' data. The web design indicator has the second lowest score because TokopediaPlay has too many ornaments in the initial menu display, making potential buyers not focus on visualizing the product they are looking for. With the extensive knowledge, curiosity, and technological skills that respondents have, they make respondents make comparisons between products on other platforms. The customer service indicator has the lowest score due to the need for more excellent and responsive service in handling consumer problems due to the robot's automatic response only.

Fulfillment is the strongest indicator of e-service quality in increasing trust. Consumers' perceptions regarding the reliability of the system in the TokopediaPlay application are pretty satisfactory and trustworthy because the Tokopedia application uses an item tracking system so that it can provide information to consumers regarding the goods ordered and features for canceling or changing product purchases when the consumer is not suitable or when they are wrong. Choose product. Thanks to the security guarantees offered, tokopediaPlay users can make transactions more safely and without worrying about fraud. More timely, accurate, safe, and reliable online store deliveries, lower waiting times, and customer risks indicate a better customer shopping experience.

Suppose a consumer checks the product and finds a defect. In that case, the seller must show a positive and responsible attitude because a positive shopping experience will increase consumer confidence and loyalty to the services provided (Hung et al., 2019). According to (Buttle, 2009), If customers are satisfied, trust will grow while risk and uncertainty are reduced.

The research results show that e-service quality does not directly have a significant impact on repurchase intention. However, the indirect influence of e-service quality has an essential impact on online repurchase intentions through consumer trust, which has complete mediation, meaning that consumer trust can bridge the influence of e-service quality on online repurchase intentions perfectly, so without the mediation of consumer trust, there is no influence of the e-service quality variable on TokopediaPlay's repurchase intention. According to (Kotler & Armstrong, 2017), Developing trust is an investment in building relationships that have long-term results. In conducting business or online business, a business actor must create a website with attractive packaging and operational quality to serve consumer e-shopping activities effectively and efficiently. An attractive site appearance, ease of obtaining information, fulfillment of goods as promised, privacy, data security and complaint services, and responsiveness in responding to problems that arise to increase trust. Supporting research by (Rita et al., 2019), consumers will make repurchases intention, Positive Word of mouth, and site visits when the consumer feels satisfaction and trust in the quality of the services provided, which consist of web design, customer service, fulfillment, and privacy.

However, in this research, repurchase intentions on live-stream shopping platforms can be influenced by social presence. This research shows that social presence from other consumers, streamers, and online platforms will increase consumers' perceived intentions to repurchase. Because consumers need social cues from streamers in live shopping and other shoppers involved to support their purchasing decisions, a lack of social presence can hinder online exchanges (Khwaja et al., 2019). Consumers not only interact with computer-mediated media but also need to communicate with other consumers in live stream shopping sales so that they are involved in the sale longer and warmer. Supporting the research of (Attar et al., 2023), social presence reduces the gap between consumers and sellers, creating an environment that encourages building trust, which leads to consumer loyalty and interest in reusing. Customers prefer to communicate via commerce and appreciate others sharing advice and information; a platform must be able to convey messages socially and express a sense of personal presence. Meanwhile, these results contradict Oliveira Huertas's (2015) and (Lim et al., 2021) research, which shows that social presence does not affect repurchase intention. Consumers are more concerned with interconnection and entertainment factors than just Social Presence, and human-like technology can understand their needs and desires over time.

The Social Presence variable has a significant effect on customer trust. The existence of live-stream shopping videos on TokopediaPlay can open sellers' insight into the potential power of visual content. Live streaming makes it easier for sellers and buyers to interact in real-time and communicate via chat features so that they can increase trust. In increasing the social presence of streamers, TokopediaPlay not only presents sellers who promote products, but sometimes they use an Influencer marketing strategy by inviting an influencer to sell products during Live stream shopping to increase brand awareness, brand trust, and sales according to the target market. Has been determined. In (J. B. Kim, 2015), a sensation of social presence can be created by interacting with the platform and presenting the function of other visitors to share ideas about products, seek feedback, and enter into deeper interactions. A website with a high social presence will convey more information and social cues and, thus, be perceived as more transparent.

In contrast, untrustworthy behavior will be easily discouraged in a more transparent environment. Social presence will also shorten the perceived social distance between buyers and

sellers (Lu et al., 2016; Pavlou et al., 2007). Supporting research by (Lu et al., 2016) also explains that social presence influences online web consumer trust in China, and sales style and other communication methods make sellers feel friendlier and warmer.

The research results show that social presence has an important impact on online repurchase intentions through customer trust, which is partial mediation, meaning that customer trust can bridge the influence of social presence on online repurchase intentions, but without consumer trust in Basically, the sense of social presence felt by consumers is able to increase online repurchase intentions. This shows that when the TokopediaPlay platform provides a good and high sense of social presence, customer trust can be increased. The results of this research support research by (Alhulail et al., 2019) which shows that customer reuse can be influenced by interactions from other people they know and trust. The social presence attribute on the website can increase interaction and share messages, suggestions and information with each other. According to (Peter & Olson, 2010) Customers who are satisfied and believe in the service provided by the company, they will buy the product again, praise the product they bought in front of other people, be less interested in competitors' brands and advertisements and buy other products from the same company.

5. Conclusion

The results show that electronic service quality does not affect online repurchase intentions. Social presence can increase online repurchase intentions. The quality of electronic services can increase consumer confidence. Social presence can increase consumer trust. Consumer trust can encourage an increase in online repurchase intentions. Consumer trust is expressed as a perfect mediation variable (complete mediation) between the electronic service quality variable and online repurchase intentions. Consumer trust is a partial mediation variable between the social presence variable and online repurchase intentions. Recommendations for future researchers Considering that the independent variable e-service quality in this study has no direct influence on repurchase intentions. The results of this research can be used as a reference for considering other independent variables that are stronger and more influential in repurchase intentions. Researchers can then conduct research with respondents from different live-stream shopping marketplace platforms and with different respondent criteria. Managerial Implications Continue to improve the quality of web design and ease of operating connection quality and minimize disruptions or technical problems with the TokopediaPlay application to retain potential consumers to buy again. Improving the quality of services in terms of reliability, responsiveness in responding to consumer complaints, and providing guarantees so that consumers feel confident about using them again. Increase social presence by presenting attractive streamers, having suitable communication methods, and mastering the products sold during live stream shopping to create a sense of trust and intention to repurchase and increase the social presence of the TokopediaPlay platform with various intensives that attract consumer attention, such as providing giveaways and flash sales. It also improves network quality when live stream shopping takes place to reach all communities in various regions.

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